

IDENTIFICATION OF SYNERGIES LIST

DELIVERABLE 7.2

Project number: 101081782

Project acronym: deCYPher

Project title: Decipher cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs) by digital tools to produce flavonoids and terpenoids

Project start date: 01 September 2023

Project duration: 48 months

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Deliverable Information	
Title	Identification of synergies list
Deliverable number	D7.2
WP number	6
Author(s)	All consortium members
Lead beneficiary	Biofaction
Type	R - Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Due date	31 August 2024

History of Changes	
Version 0.1	Draft created by UGent and Biofaction (23.08.2024)
Version 1.0	Final version approved by all Beneficiaries (29.08.2024)

Synergy activity name	What? Type of synergy activity	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to specific project output, Why? Describe the synergistic effect	Who of deCYPher?	With who?	Status of the synergistic activity	Date
Attending the KoM iCulture/deCYPher	Meetings	Presenting the deCYPher project and objectives to the iCulture consortium and visa versa of the iCulture project to the deCYPher consortium to find synergies between the two different projects and approaches	Whole deCYPher consortium	iCulture consortium	Delivered	19/09/2024 and 21/09/2024
NATO Science for Peace Programme: Advanced Research Workshop: Comparative Modernization in Biotechnology Research Infrastructures. Biotechnology: Technological Convergence and Information Hazards.	Conferences	Presenting the deCYPher project and objective to an international group of experts in the field of risk management and biosecurity. Discussing governance challenges to make sure the convergence of AI and synthetic biology doesn't lead to misuse for novel biosecurity threats. A joint publication (book chapter) is currently prepared. The collaboration with the NATO Science for Peace Programme will support deCYPher's Task 6.5. Stimulating deeper reflection about convergence of AI/ML and SynBio.	Biofaction	NATO Science for Peace Programme and International group of experts in the field of AI, synthetic biology, biosecurity and risk management	Delivered	29/04/2024
Combined artist in residency program	Other	Both EU projects aim to integrate biotechnology and computational biology/AI. Combining the resources of deCYPher and Bioindustry 4.0 to promote the artist in residency program allows to expand the outreach and impact of the training, education and reflection of the involved technologies.	FBAS, Biofaction	Bioindustry 4.0 consortium	Ongoing	
Bits in Bio event focussed on deCYPher activities	Education and training events	Bits in Bio is a global community that brings together the people from tech and biotech industries, learn from one another, and combine the best practices of the tech world with the understanding of biology.	ML6, UGent	Bits in Bio - Belgium	Ongoing	

Bioindustry 4.0 summer webinar	Meetings	Presenting the deCYPher project and objectives to the Bioindustry 4.0 consortium to find synergies between the two different projects and approaches	Biofaction, UGent	Bioindustry 4.0 consortium	Ongoing	29-30/08/2024
FAIRDOM user meetings	Other scientific cooperation	FAIRDOM is an open community-driven consortium that welcomes developers, user communities, and individual users to use and develop FAIRDOM-SEEK. DataHub is an instance of FAIRDOM-SEEK.	VIB	FAIRDOM community	Ongoing	
OECD Workshop: SynBio x AI Convergence: Leveraging foresight for anticipatory governance	Meetings	The OECD Working Party on Biotechnology, Nanotechnology and Converging Technologies (BNCT) is convening a two-day workshop with selected experts from natural and social sciences, governance and foresight, Synthetic Biology (SynBio) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The participation in the OECD workshop will support deCYPher's Task 6.5. Stimulating deeper reflection about convergence of AI/ML and SynBio.	Biofaction	OECD and International group of experts in the field of AI, synthetic biology, biosecurity and risk management.	Ongoing	21-22/10/2024